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The Practice of Japanese-Style Education in India Considering Diversity: A Study of Students in Private Schools

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Abstract

This study evaluates the applicability and perception of Japanese-style classroom management within the diverse educational landscape of India. A targeted two-hour educational intervention was conducted with 15-year-old students at an Indian private school, focusing on the theme "Indian-style classrooms, Japanese-style classrooms and supporting each other's classmates." Qualitative data collected from student worksheets were structured and evaluated using the KJ method for thematic categorization. The findings revealed a strong mutual respect between India and Japan, with students recognizing a high potential for integrating Japanese educational methods into the Indian system. Key participant strengths emerged across categories including educational drive, capacity for action, positive belief systems, and peer-to-family support structures. The study demonstrates that verbalizing these intrinsic strengths deepens teacher-student alignment and fosters inclusive, mutual peer understanding essential for managing classroom diversity.

The Practice of Japanese-Style Education in India Considering Diversity: A Study of Students in Private Schools

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The aim of this study was to research Japanese-style education that recognizes diversity: a two-hour classroom management lesson was conducted with 15-year-old Indian private school students on the theme 'Indian-style classrooms, Japanese-style classrooms and supporting each other's classmates. The students' worksheet descriptions were analyzed using the KJ method (categorizing descriptions). The results showed that the pupils felt that Japan and India have friendly relations and that Japanese education has potential in India. They also listed 'strengths' as education, ability to take action, confidence and belief, positive thinking, and support for family and friends. The verbalization of strengths could lead to teachers' understanding of their students and mutual understanding between them.

Keywords: regular classes, inclusive education, educational guidance, caste, Japanese-Style Education, Private schools

Inclusive education

The OECD (2001) definition of special needs education includes not only organic disabilities but also the educational needs of pupils deemed to arise from socio-economic, cultural, or linguistic factors. Different countries define the definition differently in which areas. Therefore, the proportion of students with special educational needs increases from country to country. The number of students with special educational needs in primary and secondary education is said to be 14% in the USA (Rotherham & Dillon, 2007) and 5% in Hong Kong (Education Bureau, 2013). The Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (2012) states that children with learning or behavioral difficulties are enrolled in regular elementary and junior high school classes at a rate of 6.5%, which may include children with developmental disabilities.

Special support education, which aims to develop children with disabilities to their full potential and ability, is essential to inclusive education. The principle of inclusive education consists in adapting the learning process to each individual so that maximum results can be achieved from all of them. Therefore, inclusive education opposes the segregation of pupils with disabilities in special education institutions (Calero & Benasco, 2015).

India is a country of diversity

The Population Division, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, United Nations Secretariat (2022) released a report on the occasion of World Population Day on 11 July. According to the report, India's population in 22 years is already 1,412 million, close to China's 1,426 million. India's population is expected to grow to 1.668 billion by 50 years, well ahead of China's 1.317 billion, which is set to decline. India has been

called the largest 'country of diversity in the world, and this diversity includes not only climate, race, and religion, but also language, culture, customs and class, and much of people's lives.

Inclusive education in India

India's Disability Rights Act (2016) emphasized the Government's commitment to inclusive education, stating that 'students with and without disabilities learn together and the teaching and learning system is appropriately adapted to meet the learning needs of students with different types of disabilities. 61% of children with disabilities aged 5-19 attend educational institutions (UNESCO, 2019). In India, persons with disabilities are 21 organic disabilities expressed in medical terms (such as intellectual, visual, hearing, speech, limb, muscular dystrophy, and emotional disability) (List of Disabilities Covered Under Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act (RPWD Act, 2022) Persons With Disabilities Act, 2016 (RPWD Act), 2022). However, students with these disabilities are generally excluded from regular schools.

Article 17 of the 1950 Constitution of India prohibits discriminatory terms meaning untouchable and also states the prohibition of discrimination based on caste. However, discrimination does exist. Disability due to culture by the caste system is determined by school policy.

Indian schools have expanded in quantity in recent years, but the completion rate of secondary education remains at 80% (UNICEF, 2021). The quality of teachers is also a challenge and corporal punishment of pupils is not uncommon (UNICEF, 2020). In other words, the SDG target of sustainable, quality education has not been reached (Rahman, 2021). The lack of experts on inclusive education, including disability and poverty, is a challenge (Taneja, Singal, & Samson, 2021). First, primary and secondary

education in India is challenged by the existence of safe and accessible schools that are free from corporal punishment of students, including those with disabilities due to the culture of the caste system.

Supporting and accepting diverse people and living harmoniously in the same society are the hallmarks of a society that recognizes diversity. Against this background, it is important to promote inclusive education that eliminates prejudice and discrimination and promotes healthy harmony in diversity. Education policy in India is gradually focusing on children and adults with special needs, with inclusive education in regular schools becoming a major policy goal (Singh, 2016).

Inclusive education in Japan

In this study, Japanese-style education is defined as education based on knowledge, virtue, and body by a group of teachers led by a homeroom teacher. Furthermore, it also involves group collaboration while considering the individual. In Japan, based on the School Education Law, special-needs schools and special-needs classes, which are separate from regular classes within elementary and junior high schools, have been established as places for children with disabilities to learn. On the other hand, Japan's Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (2017) states that "Based on the premise that there is a possibility that students with disabilities, including developmental disabilities, are also enrolled in regular classes in elementary schools and other schools, and to develop their qualities and abilities in all subjects and other classes, detailed guidance, and support according to each student's educational needs are provided It is necessary to provide concrete examples of the intention and methods of devising guidance for possible difficulties in the learning process in each subject, etc., as well as devising guidance

and support for each type of disability, to enable detailed guidance and support according to the educational needs of each student, to develop their qualities and abilities, in all classes. Furthermore, the Central Council on Education (2021) issued a report on 'Japanese-style school education in 2021: individual-optimal learning and collaborative learning. In other words, Japan will implement 'classroom school management aiming at the development of the individual and the group', as well as school health education and student guidance. To make schools sustainable against obstacles caused by the caste system in India, Japanese-style education can be used as a reference.

The Present Study

The aim of this study is to Japanese-style education that recognizes diversity in the light of disability due to the caste system. The outcome of this study will create awareness among Indian students to recognize diversity in disability due to the caste system.

Method

Willig (2001) states that qualitative research can ask questions about the process through the interactions between the helpers. The Japanese-style education classes in India were considered suitable for exploring the process of change through interactions with pupils by implementing Japanese-style education classes in regular classrooms that take into account inclusive education. The following qualitative data on the interaction between Japanese teachers and Indian pupils were collected in this study

Core data for analysis

Lesson plans by Japanese teachers (presentations in English, including videos in English). Primary data (core data for the analysis): Lesson plans (presentations in

English, including videos in English) and worksheets by Japanese teachers.

Background and demographics of research participants.

The study targets 15-year-olds in India. Note that children at the age of 15 years are in the secondary stage of education, although this varies from state to state in India. Note that about 30% of students in each school are from lower castes.

India classifies schools according to the way they are run: 1) those run by the central government and local bodies (government and local bodies), 2) those that are private but subsidized by the government and under various government regulations (private aided), 3) those that are private but subsidized by the government and under various government regulations (private aided), and 4) those that are private but under various government regulations (private aided). (Nakamura, 2006). Others include (iv) central government schools, sanctioned madrasa seminaries, and informal non-formal education: non-formal education (NFE) (Ishikawa, 2018). The Indian schools covered by the lesson plans are private schools in rural cities.

Research ethics

With the consent of the school principal, it was explained in writing that the questionnaire survey would not identify the school, district, or individual, that participation in the study was voluntary, and that consent to participate could be withdrawn during the study.

Analysis

The analysis method used the KJ method, in which the author and two researchers classified the cards with similar contents, one card with one content written on it, and the cards with similar contents were collected and classified by domain. The

author and the three raters examined the cards until they reached a consensus.

Outline of the lesson plan.

The following two hours were envisaged.

Hours and Lesson objectives

1 Pupil understands the 'Greetings from Japan' link between India and Japan.

2 The pupils will conduct a class opening lesson on 'Classes in India and Japan - Supporting each other, which is related to class management. Students will also understand the importance of mutual support.

The lesson content of the second hour in line with the objectives of this research is shown below. In addition, worksheets are included to examine the effectiveness of the Japanese-style education classes and to ensure that the content is retained.

2nd period

Title of lesson: Classrooms in India and Japan - Supporting each other in the classroom

Lesson objective: To consider the importance of supporting each other in the classroom.

Slide no. Classroom speech and content

- 1 Classroom climate in India and Japan
- 2 Lesson objectives: 1. to think about what they would like to do in the future to make their classroom (school) more enjoyable; 2. to understand what is good about their classmates.
- 3 Classroom management comprises all actions taken by teachers to create an environment that supports and promotes both academic and social-emotional learning (Everstone-Weinstein, 2006). In addition, the Japanese Ministry of Education,

Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (2017) states that classroom management is generally considered to be operated and developed by the classroom management goals and policies developed by the homeroom teacher based on the school's educational goals and the actual conditions of the classroom, and by developing the necessary conditions

- 4 Delhi School Classroom Goals. "To develop students "dependable, honest, loyal and nationalist to make our students happy". Mission "to develop excellence in the pursuit of excellence."
- 5 Classroom Goals in international schools in Mumbai. "Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all to Aristotle ", "Do not wait for someone else to come and speak for you. It's you who can change the world," attributed to Malala Yousafzai"
- 6 Classroom management in Japan. School goals and classroom goals. In Japanese schools, students create their own classroom goals in line with the school's goals. The goals of this school are ideal student, thinking student, caring student, tenacious student, and strong student. Based on this, the pupils came up with their own class goals. These class goals are 1. a disciplined class; 2. a caring class; 3. a cheerful and happy class.
- 7 The class target for 11-year-olds at this school is the most cohesive, "close-knit and energetic class in the school".
- 8 Each individual's strengths and weaknesses. Finding the good in classmates.

- 9 Who is he? Roshan. Roshan has felt isolated since childhood. He was born with a fused thumb and thumb on his right hand and was avoided by his classmates. He was helped by daily speech therapy.
- 10 Who is he? Abhishek. Abhishek became known for not only living with but successfully overcoming, this painful disorder after his critically acclaimed film *Taare Zameen Par* about his childhood dyslexia. He had communication problems as a child.
- 11 Who is he, C. Rana Daggubati. C. Rana Daggubati, the hero of the *Baahubali* series, is blind in one eye! Everyone was shocked and amazed at his immense courage in defying his visual impairment and paving the way for a successful career as an actor.
- 12 Who is she? Shuba Chandran. Shuba Chandran is a very talented dancer and the famous character 'Ramola' in a popular daily drama series. Known for. Later, despite undergoing amputation surgery, she mastered classical dance and became an inspiration to the country. Video up to 48 seconds. (Watch a video of Shuba Chandran 's classical dance).
- 13 Pros and cons Q1. What do people A-D have in common? Q2. People have their personalities and differences. How do you think you can develop your individuality? Q3. Describe your strengths and weaknesses (on the worksheet). Q4. What do you think you need to do in the classroom to keep your 'self-confidence' up?? (Write this on your worksheet) Q5. When do you think you feel uncomfortable in the classroom? (Please write this on your worksheet) Q6. Write about a time when your classmates did something nice for you that made you feel comfortable. (Write on your worksheet and sticky note)
- 14 Think about it for future repeated pandemics caused by infectious diseases. Smile and encourage each other in class to overcome fears. Support each other in class. It is important to work together in class. In this way, we all need to support each other to make the school closure as short as possible and get back to normal life. Finally, the video "What comes after the virus" Japanese Red Cross (2019). It explains that the weakness of fear is smiles and everyday life, as fear strikes people along with the virus.
- 15 The Tree of the Good Points: a class tree. If a classmate does something nice for you, write it down on a piece of paper and stick it up; stick a sticky note on Q6.

Results

Worksheet description

1. What you felt and thought about the links between Japan and India

Students stated that Japan and India have a very good relationship, e.g. 'Japan and India have a very good relationship' and 17 (33%) stated that Japan and India have a friendly relationship. They also stated that 'Japan is a very good place for peaceful education. I feel that India is a very good place for education from Japan', "I want to improve my skills with the help of Japanese education", etc., stated 15 (30%) students of the potential of Japanese education in India. One student (0.5%) stated that 'India is developing friendly relations with all countries and one student (0.5%) stated that 'I am happy to say that the Japan-India connection is a shared culture.

2. Describe your strengths and weaknesses

Fifteen (30%) pupils said family and friends, e.g. 'My family and friends are my strength', 'My friends are my strength', etc. Also, 4 (8%) pupils raised 'my strength is my education', 'I have an attitude of self-enlightenment, etc. Furthermore, 3 (6%) pupils raised will and action, e.g. 'I am not afraid to share my toughness freely', 'My strengths are my will and action', and 3 (6%) pupils raised confidence, e.g. 'My strength is that I am always confident' 'My strength is that I am always confident. 'My personality is courage. Three pupils (6%) gave courage as 'everyone looks up to me'. Two pupils (4%) said: 'I didn't find my strength.

3. What do you think you need to do in the classroom to keep your 'self-confidence' up?

Eight students (16%) raised their confidence and positivity by saying, "I have always been confident in life" and "I try to talk positively with my classmates." Seven students (14%) also raised friendships, including 'contact in the classroom' and 'I want to connect myself with my classmates and other people'. Six students (12%) gave study as 'I study a lot so I am always comfortable'. 'I need good people in the classroom. 'Teachers help me too', given by 4 (8%) pupils. (Photo: Good Point tree created by students)

Photo: Good Point tree created by students

Discussion

Strengths of Indian and Japanese students

Indian students in the practicing schools raised education, behaviour, confidence and belief, positive thinking and supporting family and friends as strengths, as well as family friends. Watanabe (2021) examines the perceived strengths of 16-year-old Japanese pupils. Japanese pupils' strengths are wisdom and knowledge (breakdown: originality, curiosity, interest, judgement, academic orientation and outlook), courage (breakdown: bravery, diligence, integrity and enthusiasm), humanity (ability to love and be loved, kindness and social intelligence) justice (breakdown: teamwork, equality and fairness, leadership) moderation (breakdown: generosity, humility, thoughtfulness, and prudence), transcendence (breakdown: self-discipline and self-control) and transcendence. Self-control), and transcendence (breakdown: aesthetics, gratitude, hope optimism, humour playfulness, spirituality). Comparing India and Japan, India places more emphasis on action, confidence in belief, and positive thinking. These can be considered possibilities for a developing India. Japanese education will need to incorporate them. On the other hand, the strengths of Japanese students are justice, moderation, and transcendence. These would need to be incorporated into Indian education.

When asked what they think they need in the classroom to remain 'self-confident', a student replied: 'I need good people in the classroom. Teachers help me too', four students (8%) gave teachers, but teachers' consideration for comfort in the classroom was the same in both India and Japan.

Expectations of Japanese education

In the first period, the students had a lesson on the links between Japan and India,

where they stated that ‘I think Japan is a very good place for peaceful education. I feel that India is a very good place for education from Japan’.15 (30%) students mentioned the potential of Japanese education in India. Although they did not talk about Japanese education, the students already had an image of Japanese education. We believe that the students accepted the practice of Japanese-style education because of this background.

Japanese-style education that takes diversity into account

The Student Guidance Proposal (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, 2022) states that “There are indeed a variety of factors involved, including factors related to relationships among friends. Schools are required to fully understand the background of such issues and, depending on the issue, organize an in-school collaborative support team consisting of the administration, student guidance supervisor, classroom/homeroom teacher, school nurse, SC/SSW, and other specialists, or a network support team in cooperation and collaboration with relevant institutions, etc., to provide planned, organized and The school is required to provide guidance and assistance in a planned, organized and continuous manner”. In other words, in Japan, however, teachers and others intervene in relationships between friends. Comparing classroom management in India and Japan, Ishikawa and Matsumoto et al. (2019) found that Indian teachers “think it is important to make discipline firm” and “it is important to make them follow the rules.” Indian teachers thought that “discipline and rules for individual and learning” were important. Furthermore, “When they fail to follow the rules, we don’t just punish them, but make them act according to their own rules, which they have thought up at the beginning. For example, when they forget to do their homework, they should not have a break or sit next to their friends (during free

time). Education in India was centered on teaching-learning. We believe that these Indian pupils rarely verbalized their strengths, comfort, etc. in class.

On the other hand, Japanese teachers, on the basis of [understanding the child], “start from [the child’s] individual and enhance the group. They “understand the individual and make it into a group” and “understand the individual and make the group better”. And, “Every child has a wish, so we support and direct it. Make the most of it. We make the best use of it. If the children know that the teacher understands them, they will change” and [understanding the children’s backgrounds, realize that they are valued, and giving direction to support] (Ishikawa, Matsumoto et al., 2019). In this one-hour lesson on understanding students, the students verbalized enough about their strengths and comfortable classrooms. They then visualized them with a good place tree. The verbalization of one’s strengths leads to the teacher’s understanding of the students. The visualization of friends’ strengths also leads to students’ understanding of students. In the future, based on these practices, it will be necessary to form a group beyond the caste system.

Future Challenges

This time was only two hours long. More practice is needed over a longer period. Furthermore, it was practiced in a private school in a rural area. Verification through practice in national, public, and private schools in urban and rural areas would be necessary to verify Japanese-style education.

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Book Review

Title	: The Changing Landscape of School Psychology
Author	: Edited by Prof. Panch Ramalingam and Dr. Suneetha J. Hangal
Publication	: Indian School Psychology Association, Puducherry (2024)
ISBN	: 978-93-91690-35-9 March 2024
Genre	: Educational Psychology and School as a Central Theme
Target Audience	: Teachers, teacher educators, educational psychologists, faculty members, mentors, clinical psychologists, medical practitioners, parents and anyone interested in transforming scenario of school psychology in our nation, policy makers with global understanding at large in school education and to the well-being of students at large.

Based on the text of “*The Changing Landscape of School Psychology*” edited by Prof. Panch Ramalingam and Dr. Suneetha J. Hangal. It is a book of compiled research articles and reviews on the Changing Landscape of School Psychology. It focused on the evolution and progress of the field of school psychology in India covering following important research excerpts:

- The growing recognition of school psychology as a profession in India
- The need for school psychologists to have independent practice
- The importance of collaboration among school psychologists, families, communities, councillors and educators
- Challenges of implementing school psychology programs

Strengths

- ❖ “The Changing Landscape of School Psychology” is an insightful and comprehensive look at how the field of school psychology has evolved over recent decades. This volume brings together contributions from leading experts who examine the multitude of expanding roles and responsibilities for school psychologists today.
- ❖ The book also discusses professional issues, school psychologists, mental health, crisis prevention or intervention, professional topics like supervision, consultation, and the role of parents in families and councillors.
- ❖ This book particularly valuable to captures the breadth of skills and knowledge required of modern school psychologists apart from their role that was narrowed around psycho-educational assessments.
- ❖ As schools have increasingly focused on things like social-emotional learning, behaviour support, and data-based decision making, the job has become far

more multifaceted. So this book focused multidisciplinary aspects as per the recommendations of NEP 2020.

- ❖ The authors have done an excellent job of analyzing the changes through both a practical and research-based lens. There are ample case studies, data, and evidence-based strategies provided.
- ❖ It also candidly examines the challenges school psychologists face trying to meet ever-increasing demands.
- ❖ The preface and introduction pages of editors Prof. Panch Ramalingam and Dr. Suneetha J. Hangal very clearly explains the necessity, relevance and cauterization for the first-hand experience of 'The Changing Landscape of School Psychology' even to the aspirants in the field of school psychology and to the advanced researchers as well.
- ❖ The book also includes references and resources for further reading and has a lots of scope for further researches in general, pure, applied, action type in psychology.

Opportunities

- The advent of Artificial Intelligence and negative impact of social media and internet are challenges to the parents and educators. This has to be considered as opportunity could be varying from individual to individual. More researches could be known to the communities extensively via social media.
- The campaign related researches for public awareness towards betterment of society and imparting ethical intricacies regarding of practices of regulations are another scope for the young researchers.

Overall

For anyone studying or currently working in the field of psychology, this is a “must-read” book. It paints a comprehensive picture of where school psychology practice stands today and thought-provoking insights into where it may be heading in the future.

Recommendation

By reviewing and analysing the complete text, this book is strongly recommended to Teachers, teacher educators, psychologists, mentors, medical practitioners, parents in families and communities and anyone interested in transforming scenario of school psychology well-being of students at large and for better living in the society.

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